

WEEK14 Reading report

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Abstract—This paper studies distributed Kalman filtering for sensor networks in which each node only communicates with its neighbors. The main contribution is that the author extends earlier distributed Kalman filtering ideas from the homogeneous sensing case to the more realistic heterogeneous sensing case, and further shows that, in a peer-to-peer estimation architecture, reducing disagreement among local estimates is as important as reducing the estimation error itself.

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Distributed estimation is a basic problem in sensor networks, especially when a large number of nodes need to estimate the state of a dynamic process without relying on a single fusion center. In a standard decentralized Kalman filtering architecture, every node may need to communicate with all other nodes, which leads to an all-to-all information flow and poor scalability. For a wireless sensor network, this is usually too expensive in communication and is not a realistic choice when the number of nodes becomes large.

This paper starts from a very practical limitation in earlier work. The previous distributed Kalman filter proposed by the same author only worked when all sensors had the same observation matrix. In other words, every node had to observe the process in essentially the same way. This assumption is restrictive, because in many real systems different sensors naturally provide different types of measurements. A camera, a range sensor, and a bearing sensor do not observe the same quantity, and even sensors of the same type may have different geometric relationships with the target. Because of this, the key motivation of the paper is to design distributed Kalman filtering algorithms that can still work when the observation matrices are different across the network.

What I think is especially interesting in this paper is that the goal is not only to estimate the state accurately, but also to make the estimates across the network remain close to each other. In a peer-to-peer architecture, there is no leader or fusion center that can be trusted more than the others. So even if some nodes estimate the state reasonably well, a large disagreement among nodes still means the network is not really acting as a coherent estimator. This viewpoint makes the paper closely connected to consensus theory and multi-agent coordination, not just Kalman filtering alone.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Consider a sensor network modeled by an undirected graph

$$G = (V, E),$$

where $V = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is the set of nodes and $E \subseteq V \times V$ is the set of communication links. Each node can only exchange

information with its neighbors. The dynamic process to be estimated is given by

$$x(k+1) = A_k x(k) + B_k w(k),$$

where $x(k) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the state and $w(k)$ is zero-mean white Gaussian process noise. The initial state is assumed to satisfy

$$x(0) \sim \mathcal{N}(\bar{x}(0), P_0).$$

The i -th sensor provides the measurement

$$z_i(k) = H_i(k)x(k) + v_i(k),$$

where $z_i(k) \in \mathbb{R}^p$, $H_i(k)$ is the local observation matrix, and $v_i(k)$ is zero-mean white Gaussian measurement noise. The noise statistics are

$$\mathbb{E}[w(k)w^\top(l)] = Q(k)\delta_{kl},$$

$$\mathbb{E}[v_i(k)v_j^\top(l)] = R_i(k)\delta_{kl}\delta_{ij}.$$

A key assumption in this paper is that the observation matrices $H_i(k)$ are not necessarily identical. This is exactly the heterogeneous sensing setting that earlier DKF methods could not handle well. Although a single node may not have enough information to observe the full state, the whole network can still be collectively observable.

If all sensor data were available at one place, then one could use a centralized Kalman filter. To connect the distributed problem with the centralized one, the paper introduces two network-wide aggregate quantities

$$S(k) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n H_i^\top(k) R_i^{-1}(k) H_i(k),$$

$$y(k) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n H_i^\top(k) R_i^{-1}(k) z_i(k).$$

These two terms are important because they contain the fused covariance information and the fused measurement information of the entire network. If each node could somehow obtain $S(k)$ and $y(k)$, then every node could perform a Kalman-type update locally.

More precisely, for node i , the micro-KF update can be written as

$$M_i(k) = (P_i^{-1}(k) + S(k))^{-1},$$

$$\hat{x}_i(k) = \bar{x}_i(k) + M_i(k)(y(k) - S(k)\bar{x}_i(k)),$$

$$P_i(k+1) = A_k M_i(k) A_k^\top + B_k Q_i(k) B_k^\top,$$

$$\bar{x}_i(k+1) = A_k \hat{x}_i(k).$$

Therefore, the real distributed estimation problem becomes the following: how can neighboring nodes cooperate so that each node can either approximate the global quantities $S(k)$ and

$y(k)$, or at least make their state estimates consistent across the network?

To describe inconsistency among local estimates, the paper also defines the disagreement potential

$$\Psi_G(\hat{x}) = \hat{x}^\top \hat{L} \hat{x} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} \|\hat{x}_j - \hat{x}_i\|^2,$$

where

$$\hat{x} = \text{col}(\hat{x}_1, \hat{x}_2, \dots, \hat{x}_n), \quad \hat{L} = L \otimes I_m,$$

and L is the graph Laplacian. This quantity gives a very clear way to measure how cohesive the estimates are over the network.

III. MAIN RESULTS

The paper presents three distributed Kalman filtering algorithms, and I think the cleanest way to understand them is to divide them into two groups.

The first group is the Type-I DKF algorithm. The idea here is to fuse the sensed data and covariance information through two identical high-pass consensus filters. Instead of assuming the sensors have the same observation model, the author applies consensus to the transformed local quantities

$$u_i(k) = H_i^\top(k) R_i^{-1}(k) z_i(k), \quad U_i(k) = H_i^\top(k) R_i^{-1}(k) H_i(k),$$

so that each node can asymptotically approximate the global averages $y(k)$ and $S(k)$. After that, each node runs a local micro-KF update. This is an important improvement over the earlier DKF because it allows heterogeneous observation matrices. In that sense, the network can act as a collective observer even though individual sensors do not observe the state in the same way.

However, the paper also points out a weakness of this approach. The high-pass consensus filter needs a relatively large gain, and in practice this means a smaller step size or a higher communication rate is required. So although Type-I DKF is conceptually natural, it is not the most attractive method when communication cost is a serious concern.

The second group is the Type-II DKF family, whose main purpose is to reduce disagreement among local estimates. Before giving the final algorithm, the author first introduces local Kalman filtering as a baseline. In this baseline method, node i only uses its own information and that of its inclusive neighbors

$$J_i = N_i \cup \{i\}.$$

Then node i computes

$$S_i(k) = \sum_{j \in J_i} H_j^\top(k) R_j^{-1}(k) H_j(k),$$

$$y_i(k) = \sum_{j \in J_i} H_j^\top(k) R_j^{-1}(k) z_j(k),$$

and performs a standard information-form Kalman update locally. This is simple and useful as a benchmark, but it does not guarantee cohesive estimates across the network.

To improve this, Algorithm 2 adds an ad hoc consensus step after the local Kalman update. If ϕ_i denotes the intermediate estimate, then the final estimate is corrected by

$$\hat{x}_i = \phi_i + \epsilon \sum_{j \in N_i} (\phi_j - \phi_i).$$

This means that each node moves its estimate toward the average of its neighbors' intermediate estimates. The idea is intuitive and directly targets the disagreement problem.

The strongest result in the paper is the continuous-time Kalman-consensus filter and the discrete-time Algorithm 3 derived from it. In continuous time, each node applies

$$\dot{\hat{x}}_i = A \hat{x}_i + K_i(z_i - H_i \hat{x}_i) + \gamma P_i \sum_{j \in N_i} (\hat{x}_j - \hat{x}_i),$$

with

$$K_i = P_i H_i^\top R_i^{-1}.$$

The extra consensus term is not just inserted heuristically. The author proves stability using the Lyapunov function

$$V(\eta) = \sum_{i=1}^n \eta_i^\top P_i^{-1} \eta_i, \quad \eta_i = x - \hat{x}_i,$$

and shows that

$$\dot{V} \leq -2\Psi_G(\eta) \leq 0.$$

This result is important because it says two things at once: the estimation error decreases, and the disagreement among local estimators is also driven down. In my view, this is the main conceptual contribution of the paper. It turns distributed estimation from a purely filtering problem into a filtering-plus-coordination problem.

Based on this continuous-time analysis, the author then gives the iterative Kalman-consensus filter

$$M_i = (P_i^{-1} + S_i)^{-1},$$

$$\hat{x}_i = \bar{x}_i + M_i(y_i - S_i \bar{x}_i) + \epsilon M_i \sum_{j \in N_i} (\bar{x}_j - \bar{x}_i),$$

$$P_i \leftarrow A M_i A^\top + B Q B^\top, \quad \bar{x}_i \leftarrow A \hat{x}_i.$$

Compared with Algorithm 2, this correction term is more systematic and is directly tied to the Kalman structure.

The simulation results are also quite clear. The author compares four algorithms: local Kalman filtering $A0$, Type-I DKF $A1$, the ad hoc consensus method $A2$, and the Kalman-consensus filter $A3$. The target is only partially observed by each sensor, since half of the nodes measure the x -direction and the other half measure the y -direction. This means individual sensors are not fully informative, but the network as a whole is collectively observable. In the reported experiments, both $A2$ and $A3$ outperform $A0$ and $A1$, and $A3$ gives the best overall performance. The paper also stresses that estimation error alone is not enough; a good distributed estimator should also provide cohesive estimates across the network. I think this is one of the most convincing parts of the paper.

IV. YOUR THOUGHTS ON FURTHER RESEARCH

This paper gives me a useful new angle for my course project. Up to now, many of my ideas have focused on formation consistency and task-driven reconfiguration in a multi-agent setting. After reading this paper, I think there is an important layer that should come before control, namely a distributed estimation layer.

For a soccer-inspired multi-agent system, each player or agent does not have direct access to the full global state. Instead, each one only has local observations, such as nearby relative positions, local spacing, or some partial tactical information. This is actually very similar to the sensor network setting in the paper. A single player may not be able to infer the whole formation, but a network of interacting players may still be able to reconstruct a global team state.

One possible direction is to define an unknown tactical state $x(k)$ that includes information such as formation center, formation orientation, local compactness, and possibly the role of a key player. Then each player i only observes

$$z_i(k) = H_i(k)x(k) + v_i(k),$$

where the matrix $H_i(k)$ depends on what the player can sense locally. In this setting, the formation estimation problem becomes a distributed estimation problem with heterogeneous observations. Then a DKF-type mechanism can be used so that each player maintains an estimate $\hat{x}_i(k)$ of the team state.

After this estimation layer, a second layer can be used for formation adjustment. For example, if $p_i(k)$ is the actual position of player i and $p_i^*(x(k))$ is the desired position generated from the estimated team state, then one may consider an objective of the form

$$J = \sum_{i=1}^n \|p_i - p_i^*(\hat{x}_i)\|^2 + \alpha \sum_{(i,j) \in E} \|\hat{x}_i - \hat{x}_j\|^2.$$

The first term measures how well the players match the desired formation, while the second term penalizes disagreement in their estimated tactical understanding. This is appealing to me because it combines physical formation consistency with information consistency.

Another direction is to connect this with dynamic reconfiguration. In my earlier project ideas, I have been thinking about the case where the movement of an important player should induce a coordinated change in the rest of the formation. This paper suggests that the trigger for reconfiguration does not need to come from a centralized command. Instead, the network can first estimate a changing latent state and then adjust the formation according to that estimate. In other words, the overall framework can become

local observations \rightarrow distributed estimation \rightarrow formation reconfiguration.

I think this makes the project more complete, because it explains not only how agents should move, but also how they know what state the team is currently in.

Finally, I also like the disagreement potential used in this paper. In the original DKF setting, it measures disagreement among local state estimates. In my project, a similar quantity

could be used to measure disagreement in tactical understanding among players or agents:

$$\Psi_G(\hat{x}) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j) \in E} \|\hat{x}_j - \hat{x}_i\|^2.$$

This could become an additional performance metric beyond geometric formation error. A team may look roughly organized in position, but if the agents internally disagree on the current tactical state, then the formation will likely break down under disturbances. So I think one meaningful extension of my project is to study both geometric coherence and estimation coherence at the same time.

Overall, this paper does not directly solve the formation control problem I care about, but it gives a very useful missing piece. It suggests that before talking about how a multi-agent system should coordinate its actions, it is worth asking how the agents can coordinate their understanding of the state first. For my project, this seems like a natural and promising next step.